

From the Edison bulb to new LED lights: the use of new glass-ceramic materials for energy-saving light sources

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ABSTRACT

Since the first electric light invented in 1802 the electric bulbs passed through noticeable technological advance, most visible in the increase of energy-to-light efficiency that has grown from 5 to 90%. In 1880 the first incandescent bulb with filament based on carbonized bamboo was commercially successful. Since 1950s the quartz glass and halogen light bulb have been produced. In 1970s compact fluorescent bulb with spiral shape was invented. After the development of GaN blue diode, white light LED (Light Emitting Diode) sources appeared. The bulbs encapsulate InGaN blue LED covered by yellow phosphor. Common yellow phosphor material is cerium-doped yttrium aluminium garnet ($\text{Ce}^{3+}:\text{YAG}$). The most efficient phosphors use rare-earth elements as dopants. After China, the main producer of rare-earths, limited exports of these materials in 2009 and 2010, a price spike occurred on stock market. After this event, there is demand on white light sources with limited content of rare-earths. One option how to overcome this issue is to use RE-free materials, mainly doped with transition metals, such as Ag, Au, Mn, Cu, Cr, Fe [1-3].

The special interest is the use of glass-ceramics that comprise wide band-gap semiconductor nanocrystals, dispersed in a glassy matrix, for a suitable application in LEDs. These nanocrystals strongly absorb photons with energies larger than their gap and transfer this energy very efficiently to lanthanide or metal transition ions. The inter-band excitation of these nanoparticles can lead to very efficient emission of doping agents by means of energy transfer. Moreover, the quantum confinement due to the nanocrystals sizes enhances the energy transfer efficiency increasing the luminescence of these systems. This efficiency is even higher in the wide band-gap semiconductors such as SnO_2 , TiO_2 or ZnO , with an energy gap over 3.0 eV, compared to others such as Si or GaAs with energy gap around 1 eV [4]. Our aim is to design, synthesize, and characterize systems based on wide band-gap semiconductors. SnO_2 , TiO_2 and ZnO has been selected with an energy gap over 3 eV. SnO_2 is an *n*-type semiconductor with a gap 3.6 eV at 300 K and it is well-known due to the potential applications in solar cells, transparent conductive electrodes and catalysis. Several works have been published related to glass-ceramics based on SnO_2 nanocrystals precipitated in a glassy matrix of silica, obtained by sol-gel method and after adequate heat treatments. Chiodini et al. [5] analyzed the broadening of the gap through the analysis of the nanocrystals size distribution, and correlate them with the quantum confinement of the nanocrystals.

Regarding TiO_2 , this semiconductor is attracting increasing attention in the decades as a host wide-gap semiconductor, with the high refractive index and high transparency in the visible and infrared regions. The additional advantages of using TiO_2 are its low fabrication cost and good thermal and mechanical stabilities. Moreover, it is an environmentally-friendly material and is generally considered non-toxic, so can not only be used as a host for luminescence and applied to LEDs and other optoelectronic devices, but can also be applied to solar cells, photocatalysts and other energy-related products [6-9].

Finally, Zinc oxide with a wide bandgap of 3.37eV has been known for efficient and bright luminescence for many years [10]. Having large exciton binding energy of ~ 60 meV, it served as a model system for understanding the properties of excitons [11,12]. The advantages of ZnO include the ability to lase as thin films [13], as random crystallites [14] and in nanostructured form [15].

Our aim is to determine the relationship between chemical composition, structure and the wavelength of the emitted light. This allows us to develop novel rare-earth free yellowish and blue light-emitting diodes based on wide band-gap semiconductors with enhancing emissivity in yellow and blue spectrum range.

Keywords: dopant, glass-ceramics, LED, rare-earth free, semiconductor, wide band-gap

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